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DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN UKRAINIAN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION DURING WARTIME

Abstract.

Ukraine, being in a military conflict, faces numerous social, economic, and political challenges. Educational institutions, especially medical ones, are under particular pressure, striving to ensure the safety and accessibility of education amidst severe restrictions and threats. The main challenges include widespread infrastructure destruction, unsafe learning and working conditions, loss of human resources, and restricted access to education for individuals in temporarily occupied territories or active conflict zones. This article is dedicated to exploring the possibilities of using distance learning technologies in higher medical education in Ukraine during the war. Research methods included a literature search in specified databases and an analysis of the main challenges and advantages of using the online learning format in a military conflict context.

The research results highlighted that military aggression significantly complicates the implementation of distance learning in medical education. The online learning format has become a key tool in ensuring the safety and accessibility of educational resources, allowing for the avoidance of health risks for students and teachers associated with their presence in hazardous zones. The use of distance technologies also increased the flexibility of the educational process and provided global access to advanced practices and knowledge. The strategies for adaptation, the necessity of technical infrastructure, and innovative approaches that help overcome the challenges of martial law in Ukrainian higher medical education and ensure its resilience and competitiveness at the international level are discussed.

Keywords: *higher medical education, distance learning, military conflict, safety, accessibility, technologies.*

Introduction

Ukraine, being in a military conflict, faces complex challenges not only of political and economic but also social nature. Educational institutions, forced to adapt to restrictions and threats, face the necessity to ensure the safety, reliability, and accessibility of education under the most difficult conditions. The main challenges are primarily related to the widespread destruction of educational infrastructure, dangerous conditions for life and health in learning and work environments, losses in human resources, reduction in the contingent of higher education seekers, lack of administrative control, and access to education for citizens in temporarily occupied territories or active conflict zones [4].

One of the important tasks is ensuring the continuity of education, especially in medical universities, where the training of future doctors is extremely important for the nation's health. Distance learning technologies become an important tool in providing access to educational resources under such conditions.

The aim of the work was to explore the possibilities of using distance learning technologies in higher medical education in Ukraine during the war.

Materials and methods

To achieve this aim, a literature search was conducted in specified databases, such as Google Scholar,

Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed Medline, and Embase, as well as other open sources. The main aspects considered included the challenges faced by students and teachers, the advantages of using the online learning format, and the strategies used to support educational activities in a military conflict context.

Results

As the research results showed, Russian military aggression has caused many challenges regarding the implementation of distance learning in medical education during the war.

Safety and accessibility of resources. Under martial law, the educational process in higher education institutions has become extremely vulnerable, as the threat concerns not only the normal course of the educational process but also the very lives of its participants. Distance learning can become the only option, as it provides maximum possible safety through the dispersion of participants in the educational process and the possibility of their localization in the most protected places. The main problem is whether it is possible today to implement distance learning so that the possibilities of face-to-face learning are sufficiently realized. Experience has shown that this is possible with the broad and rational use of innovative pedagogical technologies in

combination with the achievements of modern information and communication technologies [3].

Students can access course materials remotely from a safe haven. The teaching staff can offer students collaborative and supportive learning services through online platforms without worrying about their safety [9].

Quality of clinical training. The inability to gain sufficient practical experience and clinical training becomes a serious challenge for medical education. The use of virtual tools and simulators can, in some cases, compensate for this shortfall but not completely replace real clinical experience.

Psychological support for students and teachers: Military events can cause stress and anxiety among participants in the educational process. Effective psychological support and counseling services are critically important for maintaining the mental health of students and teachers. According to GoGlobal, 54% of Ukrainian educators have experienced professional "burnout" due to teaching during wartime, and 46% identified psychological support as a priority need [2].

Advantages of distance learning technologies during wartime

Flexibility and safety. Distance learning technologies allow for ensuring safety and flexibility in the educational process even under difficult wartime conditions. They help avoid health risks for students and teachers related to being present in hazardous zones.

Global access to knowledge. The use of the online learning format promotes the involvement of international experts and resources, significantly enhancing the quality of education. Students can access advanced practices and knowledge from around the world, which is important in the context of medical education.

Scalability and efficiency. Online learning allows for scaling educational programs and ensures a stable educational process even under unpredictable circumstances. This reduces the impact of military events on the operation of higher educational institutions and provides continuous education.

Experience of implementation in ukrainian higher medical education

Ukrainian medical educational institutions are implementing new formats of distance learning, such as: 1) involving interns and junior specialists in providing medical care and other activities; 2) providing the opportunity for temporarily displaced students to study online at other universities without transferring to them. Various online platforms, software products, and other means are used in these programs [8].

Strategies for adaptation, ensuring technical infrastructure, and using innovative approaches are also important [7,11].

Adaptation strategies. Ukrainian educational institutions actively adapt to the challenges of military conflict by implementing distance learning technologies. This includes developing specialized online courses, webinars, and using modern educational platforms to provide access to educational resources.

Technical infrastructure. Assessing the stability of internet connections in various regions of Ukraine is

crucial for the successful conduct of online classes. Ensuring adequate technical equipment and software for students and teachers is a key aspect of implementing distance technologies.

Innovative approaches. The use of medical simulators and virtual laboratories allows for practical training of students in a virtual environment. This helps to compensate for the loss in clinical training due to limited access to real clinical facilities in the conflict zone [1,10].

Active mastery of modern technical communication capabilities by participants in the educational process, such as "student-teacher" communication, has contributed to the continuity of the educational process, although technical support and the Internet need further improvement for their use in the educational process [5].

Safety and support measures

Cybersecurity: Implementing security measures to protect confidential information and personal data of students and teachers is extremely important in wartime conditions and the growing cyber threat.

Psychological support: Ensuring access to psychological support and counseling for students and teachers experiencing stress and anxiety due to military events is an important aspect of maintaining their mental health [6].

Prospects and future challenges

Innovations in education: The development and integration of new technologies into educational resilience strategies will enable Ukrainian higher medical education to withstand the challenges of military conflict and remain competitive at the international level.

Optimization and adaptation: Continuing to optimize distance learning systems and adapt to changing wartime conditions is an important task for the future.

Conclusions

The study of distance learning in Ukrainian higher medical education during the military conflict emphasizes the necessity and importance of this educational format for ensuring the continuity of the educational process and the safety of its participants. Military actions have led to serious challenges for medical universities, including widespread infrastructure destruction, threats to the safety of participants in the educational process, losses in human resources, and reduction in the contingent of students studying in temporarily occupied territories. Distance technologies have proven to be an effective tool for ensuring access to education, particularly due to their flexibility and the ability to avoid health risks. The main advantages include global access to knowledge, scalability and efficiency of educational programs, as well as maintaining the educational system under conditions of instability. The research conclusions underscore the need for further support and development of distance learning as a strategic direction for Ukrainian higher medical education, aimed at maintaining the quality of education and competitiveness in the international context.

References:

1. Alcázar Artero PM, Greif R, Cerón Madrigal JJ, Escribano D, Pérez Rubio MT, Alcázar Artero ME, López Guardiola P, Mendoza López M, Melendreras

- Ruiz R, Pardo Ríos M. Teaching cardiopulmonary resuscitation using virtual reality: A randomized study. *Australas Emerg Care*. 2024 Mar;27(1):57-62. doi: 10.1016/j.aucec.2023.08.002.
2. Global Office. The impact of war on educators. Available from: https://globaloffice.org.ua/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/prezentatsya_vpliv-vijni-na-osvityan.pdf
3. Golovan V, Horlichenko M, Drozdov M. Distance learning in military higher education institutions under martial law. *Distance Education in Ukraine: Innovative, Normative-Legal, Pedagogical Aspects*. 2023 Feb 24;183-195. doi: 10.18372/2786-5495.1.17321.
4. Iliichuk L. Ensuring the quality of higher education under martial law: results of information-analytical research. *NEW INCEPTION / Theory and Practice of Specialist Training*. 2023;1-2(11-12).
5. Kavyn V. Comparison of the results of studying by the students of the "Clinical Anatomy and Operative Surgery" module with different forms of the educational process in conditions of social shocks in Ukraine. *Georgian Med News*. 2023 Jul-Aug;(340-341):176-179.
6. Kipenskyi A, Pidbutska N, Ponomariov O. Features of overcoming stress during martial law by teachers of higher education institutions. *Theory and Practice of Social Systems Management*. 2023;1:65. doi: 10.20998/2078-7782.2023.1.05.
7. Londar L, Pietsch M. Providing Distance Education During The War: The Experience Of Ukraine. *ITLT*. 2023 Dec;98(6):31-51. doi: 10.33407/itlt.v98i6.5454.
8. Popova OI, Il'ina-Stohnienko VYu, Herasymenko OA. Successful cases of distance learning in medical educational institutions of Ukraine during martial law. *Academic Visions*. 2023;(18). Available from: <https://academy-vision.org/index.php/av/article/view/260>
9. Rajab KD. The Effectiveness and Potential of E-Learning in War Zones: An Empirical Comparison of Face-to-Face and Online Education in Saudi Arabia. *IEEE Access*. 2018;6:6783-6794. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2800164.
10. Rayamajhi S, Machin A, Breen C, Gebreheat G, Paterson R. Quality and impact of pharmacology digital simulation education on pre-registration healthcare students: A systematic literature review. *Nurse Educ Today*. 2024 Sep;140:106295. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2024.106295.
11. Sherman M, Puhovskiy E, Kambalova Y, Kdyrova I. The future of distance education in war or the education of the future (the Ukrainian case study). *Futurity Education*. 2022;2(3):15-24. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.57125/FED/2022.10.11.30>